

STAGES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE WORK OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM

Ataxanov Shuxrat Turaxanovich

Teacher of the Military Training Center

Mirzo Ulugbek National University of Uzbekistan

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Abstract

This article describes the stages of the implementation of the effectiveness of the work of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, the formation and strengthening of modern concepts about the protection of the Motherland, its preservation, the worldview, personal beliefs on this issue, the preparation of young people for military service, the organization of educational activities that help.

Key words: issues of youth, military, patriotic, devoted, high, spiritual and spiritual education. The concept of military-patriotic education of youth – developed on the basis of the basic principles and priorities of the state youth policy implemented in the country, urgent tasks and ways to solve them related to educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotic education in the current complex globalization, rapid development of information and communication technologies, interaction with government and non-governmental organizations, family, mahallas, educational institutions determine the role of and the importance of institutions in this matter, their interaction, taking into account national and international legal norms.

In today's era of globalization and intense competition, armed conflicts and confrontations taking place in different parts of the world, new threats and risks pose urgent urgent tasks for us.

It is in such conditions that the education of the youth of our country in the spirit of patriotism, including military-patriotic, high spiritual and moral values, deep penetration into their consciousness of the need to preserve peace and harmony as the apple of their eye, "the people and the army are one body, one soul!" It is necessary to combine the efforts and capabilities of ministries and departments responsible for the education of young people on the basis of one idea, one goal.

The education of patriotic, devoted and ambitious youth by instilling from early childhood in the hearts and minds of young people the most important concepts, life and professional skills related to the preservation of our Motherland as the apple of our eye in any difficult and difficult situation, glorifying its glory to the world, based on science and education, as well as national values, is the main essence concepts.

Educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit "Motherland is great, duty is holy!" it is organized under a conceptual idea in which the main task is to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism, comprehensive development, and the formation of a personality with firm beliefs and convictions.

The main content and essence of this idea is to educate the younger generation in the spirit of respect and respect for our great history, age—old values, the elevation of the national spirit

and pride, the need to preserve and protect priceless wealth - peace and tranquility, readiness, if necessary, to defend the sovereignty of the country.

The purpose of military-patriotic education of young people is to consolidate such important qualities among young people as activity in various sectors of society, especially in types of public service related to the military sphere, commitment to the Constitution and military duty, high responsibility and responsibility for the fate of their country and people.

The main objectives of the military-patriotic education of youth are:

the creation of a unified education system aimed at the development of military-patriotic feelings, spiritual qualities and intellectual potential of youth;

educating young people in the spirit of the national idea and devotion to the Motherland, deeply penetrating into their consciousness that protecting the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;

wide propaganda among the youth of our great history, the rich spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, the contribution of such field commanders as Jalaliddin Manguberdiev, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur to the development of world civilization and military art;

To instill in young people such qualities as patriotism and heroism shown by our compatriots who gave their lives in the name of freedom and independence of the Motherland, loyalty, dedication, perseverance and courage, as well as the realization that the protection of the motherland, family, parents and children is a sacred duty to the memory of the people and ancestors;

the formation of young people's skills in approaching the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world, based on our national interests, a healthy worldview against destructive ideas, vices that destroy morality, lead young people into decline, biased information disseminated by the media, including through the worldwide Internet information network;

further increase of trust and respect for the national army in the minds of young people by holding a series of military-patriotic events and military-patriotic training camps "school of courage" in the regions, strengthening the understanding that military service is a sacred duty of a citizen of Uzbekistan;

improving the quality of teaching the subject of pre-conscription primary training in secondary schools, focusing on strengthening the educational and material base and thereby increasing the level of knowledge and initial military training of young people studying about military service, the legal basis for its passage;

To be ready to defend the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but also in all spheres of life, to be selfless for the Motherland is a requirement of today, to widely bring life examples and effective means to the youth masses;

formation of young people's characteristics of adherence to the traditions and values of their ancestors and ancestors related to the protection of the Fatherland;

Formation and strengthening of modern ideas about the protection of the Motherland, its preservation, worldview, personal beliefs on this issue, organization of educational activities that contribute to the preparation of young people for military service, increase their spiritual and moral training.

From the above, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit is determined by how much this process positively affects the upbringing of a harmonious generation, the level of patriotism of young people. An important condition for determining the level of effectiveness in military-patriotic education is the systematic consideration and analysis of factors favorably influencing the further development and improvement in real life of such qualities as patriotism, military duty, and loyalty to military traditions among young people. Special attention is paid to carrying out systematic work on educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, high spiritual and moral values. In this regard, the children's and youth movement "support of the Motherland" was organized throughout the country. It should be noted that the creation of groups of this movement in all secondary schools, covering more than 20 thousand students, makes a worthy contribution to fostering in the hearts of our children a sense of love and devotion to the Motherland.

The activities outlined in the concept are carried out in the following five stages:

a) the first stage (3-7 years) is carried out in preschool educational organizations, taking into account the characteristics inherent in children of this age, including such needs as the ability to manage their emotions, behavior, the foundations of personal qualities, the emergence of interest in social motives and national traditions, self-expression and success.

At this stage, events are held with children aimed at the formation of such noble qualities as national pride, hard work, love and protection of the Motherland, respect for state symbols, great ancestors, historical monuments, mutual assistance, kindness, including teaching poems, fairy tales, melodies and songs, sports and national games, theatrical and stage performances;

B) the second stage (7-10 years) - events are held in the lower grades of general education and specialized educational organizations, as well as in mahallas, taking into account the age characteristics of this category of youth.

At this stage, comprehensive measures will be carried out to foster a sense of pride and love for the symbols of the Motherland and the state, respectful and respectful attitude towards the elderly, respect for national customs and traditions, and develop a sense of pride in belonging to the Republic of Uzbekistan;

c) the third stage (11-17 years old) - events are held in the senior classes of general education and specialized educational organizations, as well as in mahallas, taking into account the age characteristics of this category of youth.

At this stage, the main attention is paid to increasing young people's interest in military service, a sense of pride in their armed forces, the development of physical abilities, educating them as physically healthy, spiritually mature, comprehensively developed, independently thinking people, as well as the broad involvement of young people in the activities of the children's and youth military patriotic movement "Support of the Motherland" ;

g) the fourth stage (18-21 years) - covers students of higher educational institutions, unorganized youth, conscripts, conscripts called up for military service under contract, cadets of higher military educational institutions, as well as youth working in labor collectives.

At this stage, the main focus is on improving the physical and spiritual abilities of young people, leadership skills and intellectual potential, general and professional qualifications, encouraging them to regularly work on themselves, lead a healthy lifestyle and achieve this.

Events with the participation of conscripts, enlisted men, newly conscripted into military service under contract, as well as cadets of higher military educational institutions are conducted on the basis of plans and programs of ministries and departments that are part of the Armed Forces;

d) the fifth stage (22-30 years) - the events cover unorganized youth in the neighborhood, youth working in labor collectives, as well as young enlisted men, sergeants and contract officers.

At the final stage, the main attention will be paid to increasing the level of social activity, civic responsibility, spirituality, the formation of citizens with positive values and qualities and able to manifest them in the process of creation in the interests of the country, strengthening the state, ensuring its vital needs and sustainable development.

Many works have been written in the mystical doctrine of the perfect man. One of these people is Aziziddin Nasafi, who lived in the XIII century, who in his treatise entitled "the perfect man" describes the perfect man and writes: "Know that a perfect man is called a person who has matured in Sharia, Tariqa and truth, and if you do not understand this expression, let me say it to another with the phrase: know that a perfect person is a person who let a thing ripen: a good word, a good verb, good morality and enlightenment." A person endowed with these qualities protects himself from lies, deception and all dirt, always living

with good intentions and ready to do good deeds.

A person with good qualities can climb the career ladder to a perfect person. A perfect person is considered the most perfect, wise and wise of people. A perfect man is a noble family that grows out of people. People achieve perfection in the process of moral and spiritual purification.

The main sign of perfection, according to scientists, is to follow the path of truth and benefit people. The more people a person benefits by his intention, word and deed, the more people his behavior directs bad people to the right path and the more selfless he is on the path to truth, the more perfect a person he becomes.

"The upbringing of the younger generation requires an adequate approach to the real requirements of the country's development, special precision. This definition should express the level of our modern self-awareness as a nation and people, as well as our national thinking required by modern students engaged in development.

As long as the fate of the great Uzbekistan, whose future we want and are building, is linked to the ideal of a perfect man, we cannot interpret it separately from the demands of the future. Our ancestors wrote many manuals and books about the upbringing of an ideal person, a perfect person. "Nightmare" by Kaykovus, "Gulistan", "Boston" by Saadi, "Tuzuklari Timur" by Amir Temur, "Bahoristan" by Abdurrahman Jami, "Mahbubul Kulub" by Alisher Navoi, "Akhlaki Muhsini" by Hussein Waiz Koshifi and others. These works convey such oriental human qualities as justice, honesty, purity, purity, correctness, truthfulness, humanity, enlightenment.

Alisher Navoi's work "Nasaimul Mukhabbat" lists the features and oriental virtues of a perfect man. Among them, the great thinker names the following: satisfaction with halal food, earning a living from his profession, observing Sharia, as well as modesty, politeness, compassion, generosity, courage, patience, loyalty and fidelity.

Thus, in the past, a unique moral code of the ideal person was developed, and to possess these qualities was considered the dream of every person.

Ideas about the ideal person have always had and have great social and moral significance. It serves to glorify a person, to perform noble and good deeds, to strengthen affection, devotion and devotion.

At all times, at every minute, they remind people of their humanity, help them to refrain from evil, mean deeds, inappropriate behavior and deeds, create the basis for awakening faith and conscience in them.

Based on the above considerations, perfect human qualities generally include:

1. Mental maturity;
2. Moral purity.
3. Physical health;

A perfect person who thinks in a new way, in the spirit of independence, must first of all be a person with a high sense of civic duty. Simply put, the ideal person today:

Not "What has this country, this society given me?",

"What have I given my country, my country?" - one should think and always live with this belief.

Responsible persons in the Armed Forces system should educate all military personnel under their command as spiritually and morally mature, intellectually capable and in the spirit of patriotism, instill in them a sense of pride in their history and for being defenders of the Motherland, should strive to shoot, improve their combat capability and thinking, improve combat and service willingness to strengthen a sense of belonging to the events taking place around, to acquire high moral and spiritual qualities. Then they are considered to have fully and faithfully fulfilled their duties.

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2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State youth policy".
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 267 dated June 29, 2023.
4. Munavvarova M. The spiritual roots of the national idea. -T.: "Spirituality", 2011.ure, more precisely, from the demands of the future of humanity on a large scale."

